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CREATING MEANINGFUL BODILY EXPRESSION IN VIRTUAL WORLDS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes an investigation into possible participatory design methods for creating an avatar's performance to support meaningful interpersonal interaction in virtual worlds. The questions proposed for this study include how to observe and analyse people's bodily expression and how to use that material in creation of meaningful animations of bodily expression that might be incorporated in avatar behaviour. Three possible approaches were identified and evaluated in practice: observation in public places, role-play, and analysing movie clips. Observations in public places and role-play appear to be limited and unproductive in this study. Analysing movie clips could be considered as a useful approach to engage people in creating meaningful bodily expression for avatars. Besides, a preliminary scheme for understanding people's experiences and viewpoints on bodily expressions of interpersonal interaction was concluded as follows: the phenomenon of empathy, the balance of status, the effects of environment, and the difference reactions in gender.

Keywords: Avatar, Meaningful Bodily Expression, Movie Clips

INTRODUCTION

In nonverbal communication, facial expression and body movement are two channels for conveying emotions, status and attitudes. In virtual worlds, however, it is almost impossible to see both facial expression and body movement because of the

avatar's actual distance and the contents of screen (Salem and Earle, 2000). Salem and Earle (2000) suggested the development of two sets of animations: "one set is implemented through gesture, the other is through facial expression." There have been extensive inquiries concentrated on the use of facial expression and body movement for online environments. For example, Fabri et al (2002) created seven different categories of facial expression according to Ekman and Friesen's Facial Action Coding System then investigated further into online interpersonal communication (2004, 2005). In Slater et al (2000), actors could control their avatar's body movement to display the expressiveness in a system for virtual rehearsal. This system gives users greater freedom to arrange the position and the degree of an avatar's body but users need time to put their body in the right position. It seems a conflict because real-time is one feature of interaction. Thus, this dilemma is an opportunity for designers to create an avatar's bodily expression to support online communication.

Creating bodily expression appropriate for computer-mediated interaction seems not easy because body movement has high variability. Conveyance and recognition of bodily expression is influenced by many factors such as personality, culture, and the social content (Gillies et al, 2004; Kleinsmith et al, 2006). For helping designers to consider all the necessary areas of action representations, Manninen (2003) illustrated the concept of perceivable interaction forms based on Habermas's communicative action theory that is analyzing and describing the interaction phenomena of real-life.

Traditionally, designers use universal techniques to create animated actions with imagination and accepted conventions. These accepted conventions are aimed to help the audience in situations that they can control. In virtual worlds, individuals may need more subtle actions to deal with unpredictable situations of interaction. It is possible that participatory design methods might help to solve this problem.

CONTEXTUAL REVIEW

Avatars in Virtual Worlds

The origin of avatar is a Sanskrit word in Hinduism for meaning an incarnation of an immortal being (Waggoner, 2009). Hindus believe that God takes birth in a human body when it comes to this world. However, with the rise of computer technology and the internet, the term ‘avatar’ has been applied to representation of participants in videogames, computer-mediated communication (CMC) and relevant fields. It is believed that the first practical Avatar-like construct, in 1972, was role-play in the text game Dungeons and Dragons. In 1978, Roy Trubshaw and Richard Bartle developed the first multi user-game (MUD) at Essex University. It was the first time that players could control their ‘characters’ to interact with others.

The modern concept of an avatar for the on-screen representation of the user was introduced in the computer game Habitat in 1985. Following Habitat, the visual persona of players became well established in later games. In 1992, Neal Stephenson’s novel ‘Snow Crash’ used the term ‘Avatar’ to mean an online virtual person, possibly the first example of this usage. With the popularisation of the internet, avatars are considered as interactive, social representations of users, aiding users to develop and keep interpersonal relationships in virtual worlds (Meadows, 2008). Thalman (2001) noted that avatars have three outstanding functions: “the visual embodiment of the user, means of interaction with world, and means of sensing various attributes of the world.”

In this research, virtual worlds are defined as computer-based simulated environments where CMC users interact with other online users. As for avatars, they are images (or animated images) used by CMC users to represent them in virtual worlds such as the animated avatar used in games and animated emoticons inserted in text messages. These virtual worlds and avatars are depicted in the form of textual, 2D, or 3D graphics.

Nonverbal Communication

Comparing with verbal communication, nonverbal communication (NVC) is often assumed more spontaneous and harder to fake. Its signals usually complement verbal communication because it could elaborate and support the verbal aspects of message. Sometimes, nonverbal signals could signify emotions, attitudes or experiences that are difficult to express through a verbal approach (Argyle, 1990). The common channel of NVC includes facial expression, gaze, gestures, posture, bodily contact, vocal behaviour, clothes, and other aspects of appearance. However, some of channels are performed in linguistic form. The sign language of the deaf, for example, is made up from the hand movements but these gesticulations are mostly linguistic (Knapp and Hall, 2010). Thus, NVC is defined as the process of communication by means of sending and receiving messages without linguistic form.

Figure 1 The paradigm of NVC (taken from Argyle, 1990)

The field of NVC is extremely complicated because of meaningfulness. Argyle (1990) described that the basic paradigm of NVC includes encoding and decoding of nonverbal signals (see Figure 1). A nonverbal signal of a sender’s state is encoded then this signal may be decoded by a receiver. Basically, the contribution of this encoding-decoding paradigm is aiding investigators to distinguish between focus on encoding and on decoding.

The role of encoder and decoder are always shifting in interpersonal interaction because of alternate sending and receiving. We may be aware or unaware our nonverbal behaviour due to encoding and decoding with varying degrees of awareness and control in this process of communication (Knapp and Hall, 2010). According to the intention of nonverbal behaviour, Ekman and Friesen (1969) provided two general categories for behavioural messages that are the ‘informative act’ and the ‘communicative act’. These two categories on the part of both encoder and decoder may be misinterpreted because of role and situational considerations.

On the whole, people can show emotional expression, attitudes, and status in the various nonverbal behaviour that are manifested by the body. Knapp and Hall (2010) pointed out that body movement and position include gestures, posture, touch behaviour, facial expression, eye behaviour and vocal behaviour. Each of these body movements functions in a distinctive approach (Argyle, 1990) and some research have focused on specific movements - e.g. work on facial expression by Ekman and Friesen (1975) or investigation in gesture and posture by Lamb and Watson (1979), Pease (1981), and Kendon (2004). Although these specific movements are subtle, they are essential competences in holistic activity. For designers, we have to look into how these competences in a synergy address the issue of interpersonal communication. Based on this reason, the term ‘bodily expression’ is used in this research.

Emotions

We know that emotions are our natural instincts and every factor in our life may arouse these natural instincts. As Lupton (1998) described, “emotions are phenomena that are shaped, experience and interpreted through social and culture processes.” Our sensation is always affected by experiencing real or imagined events, action, and symbol. Because of the wholeness of sensorial information from the external and internal physical conditions, emotions are not only defined as knowledge by acquaintance but also personal experiences of self-evident (Chaudhuri, 2006). It shows that our daily life has been weightily influenced by emotions and they are

reflected in physiology, expression and behaviour.

Emotions are an important part of social communication and play a significant role in interpersonal interaction. From Plutchik’s perspective, emotions have two main functions: the first function is to provide information about intentions or probable behaviour to others and the second function is to increase the opportunity of survival when individuals are faced with emergencies (Strongman, 2003). O’Shaughnessy and O’Shaughnessy (2003) mentioned another three points: one is to contribute to social control in some emotions which volute social standard, another is the display of emotion playing a role in persuasion to indicate commitment to a particular position, and the other is “to make up for the insufficiency of reason.” Furthermore, Ekman (1999) said that the primary function of emotions is to stimulate the organism to cope with important interpersonal conflicts rapidly. Based on these perspectives, emotions could be considered as protective reactions to adjust ourselves to our life and aid us to develop social relationships.

Conceptual Framework

Balder et al (1999) mentioned that the method through a deeper look into psychological and cognitive models of behaviour is a promising approach to create an avatar’s natural movement. Avatar designers may create appropriate bodily expression for users because of exploring the field of expressive behaviours deeply. But there is a question that is how to undertake a deeper look into psychological and cognitive models of behaviour. Argyle’s (1990) encoding-decoding paradigm of nonverbal communication provides the conceptual framework for transforming people’s bodily expression into an avatar’s bodily expression (Figure 2).

Figure 2 The transformation of creating an avatar’s bodily expression

Before creating an avatar's bodily expression, designers are assumed to decode people's bodily expression. Designers could observe people's bodily expression and interpret by themselves. However, interpreting by individual designers may not be sufficient because bodily expression may vary from person to person and context to context. In response to this, the aim of a participatory method would be to involve diverse stakeholders in the process of decoding and encoding.

METHODS

Argyle's encoding-decoding paradigm of NVC provides the conceptual framework for transforming people's meaningful bodily expression into an avatar's bodily expression, and this study was conducted to test possible approaches. The questions proposed for this research include how to observe and analyse people's bodily expression and how to use that material in the creation of meaningful animations of bodily expression that might be incorporated in avatar behaviour. Three possible approaches were identified and evaluated in practice. These approaches are: 1. observation in public places, 2. role-play, and 3. analysing movie clips.

1. Observation in Public Places

We might observe bodily expression in normal interaction since NVC signals occur in daily life (Argyle, 1990; Knapp and Hall, 2010). Observing in public places was thought a possible approach to acquire people's bodily expression. For testing this idea, two public places of Sheffield: the Moor and the Peace Gardens were selected. The Moor is a busy shopping street. The Peace Gardens is a popular inner city square with engaging water features. Photography and note-taking were used for recording people's activity during observation.

2. Role-Play

Role-play was thought to be another approach to obtain the data of bodily expression since its idea derives from daily activities. Role-players assume specific roles in a particular situation and change their behaviour to fulfil the role (Van Ment, 1999).

Argyle (1990) mentioned that role-play is an improvement on posing and he adopted the method sometimes in his NVC study. For testing this approach, one role-play game was constructed in Taipei. Three Taiwanese participants including one male and two females were invited.

In the beginning, several scenarios and different roles such as the interaction among project manager, designer, and customer were discussed. Then, three participants took on different roles to play. Video recording was used to record participants' bodily expression.

These first two methods were found to be unproductive as discussed below but the third approach was more effective.

3. Analysing Movie Clips

In movie and TV clips, bodily expression could be observed through the performance of professional actors. Through actors' performance, audiences come to understand dramatic characters and involve in the story (Philips, 2009). In addition, rich bodily expression can be observed from movies and TV series. Therefore movie and TV clips would seem as potential rich resource material to encourage participants' reflections and discussions.

Selecting potential clips to discuss with participants is very important, especially from the great amount of films available. A semi-structured questionnaire with both closed-ended questions and open-ended questions was seen as a possible method to identify useful films and scenes.

Subjects from a variety of cultural backgrounds were included in the study. Since the aim is to evaluate methods rather than generate highly generalisable data, this created no problems in practice and participants tended to contribute in similar ways regardless of backgrounds.

Four British males, two Malaysian females, three Taiwanese males, and two Taiwanese females were invited to answer the semi-structured questionnaire. These respondents considered that they needed time

to answer these questions so every participant took 3 to 4 days to fill out the questionnaire (Figure 3). When receiving feedback, additional questions that were from respondents' answers were asked for obtaining more information from respondents and observing respondents' reactions. After the brief discussions following the semi-structured questionnaire, respondents who like to share their viewpoints in detail were invited for discussions (mixture group and individual).

Figure 3 Questionnaires with respondents' feedback

At least 20 films such as drama films, action films and sci-fi films were suggested in these respondents' answers. 10 DVD were borrowed for selecting clips because some films were not released at that time. There are two main considerations when selecting movie clips for interviews. Firstly, interpersonal interaction is the subject in this investigation so the interaction between actors is the first consideration.

The second consideration is the degree of the close-up of actor's body. Close-ups are one of the standard shots adopted in the footage. In movies and TV series, actor's performance is always framed tightly with close-ups, especially facial expression. However, designers should look into how different parts of body movement in a synergy address the issue of interpersonal interaction. Based on these two considerations, two potential clips were selected from the suggested British TV series - The Office.

Two clips as artefacts were used for interviews to observe and analyse bodily expression. Two approaches including a focus group and one-on-one interviews were adopted and seven participants were invited for discussing these two movie clips. Two Taiwanese males and a Taiwanese female were invited in the focus group. Two Malaysian females, one Taiwanese female and one British male were invited in one-on-one interviews.

The data of interviews were collected by video recording, sound recording and note-taking. In addition, to avoid influencing participants' judgements on bodily expression, the sound was off when participants watched these two clips. In the beginning, participants were informed the characters of the first clip. Next, participants were asked to judge actors' bodily expression. Every participant was allowed to control the frame and the time of the clip. Then, participants were informed the story of the clip to answer perspectives and relevant experience. Some additional questions were asked from participants' responses for discussing in depth. The discussion of the second clip was undertaken by the same procedure.

RESULTS

Three possible methods for observing people's bodily expression have been tested including observation in public places, role-play, and analysing movie clips. The results of these methods are as below:

Observation in Public Places

After observing in these two public places of Sheffield: the Moor and the Peace Gardens, people appeared to present bodily expression rarely. On the other hand, negative emotions such as anger and sadness appear to be impossible to show in public places. Based on these concerns, obtaining the data of bodily expression from public places seems not a productive approach.

Role-play

The role-play game was undertaken by three Taiwanese participants who took on different roles to play. In the process of role-play, specific bodily

expression could be observed because of arranged scenarios. However, participants seemed to feel uncomfortable in front of camera and did not present bodily expression very well because they are not professional actors. (Although this was seen as unproductive in this early investigation, later in the research some role-play methods were developed to good effect and will be reported in future publications.)

Analyzing Movie Clips

In the interviews, participants were able to express themselves freely on the emotion and bodily expression being ported and this would seem most productive of these three methods used. All participants, from a variety of cultural backgrounds identified embarrassment in clips when the actors' hands cover mouth or face in particular situations. In addition, participants reflected their experience to explain actors' performance.

In the end, four findings are concluded as below:

The Phenomenon of Empathy

The definition of empathy in Cambridge Dictionary Online is "the ability to share someone else's feelings or experiences by imagining what it would be like to in their situation." It helps us to address a wide spectrum of emotional issues, especially in interpersonal communication. Ickes (1997) stated that empathy as a complicated form of psychological assumption integrates observation, memory, knowledge, and reasoning to yield insights into the thoughts and feelings of others.

In the beginning, none of the participants were informed about the story of the clips but they still could interpret actors' feelings because of empathy. Based on the observation of bodily expression, participants appeared to imagine they were the character of clips. As one of the participants said "*...when I laugh loudly in a silent place, I will try to control myself like this lady...I also use hand to cover mouth when I worry to exclaim...*" Another interview extract mentioned "*...I imagined I was the woman and looked for any reason to explain why I did this motion...*" Participants appeared to reflect

themselves then tried to find same reasons why they might use the actor's bodily expression.

The Balance of Status

People encode and decode nonverbal behaviour with varying degrees of awareness and control (Argyle, 1990). Sometimes we encode a nonverbal behaviour spontaneously but we are aware of what we are doing next second. If this behaviour is unsuitable in the situation, we may do other behaviour to balance our status.

In the first clip, a woman uses hands to cover her mouth because she laughs loudly in the office. In the second one, a woman uses hands to cover her face as she weeps in front of colleagues. Although two clips show different emotions via facial expression, all respondents felt the motion of hands shows the status of embarrassment. As one of the participants mentioned "*...I think it is very impolite to laugh loudly in the silent place such as library or office. And my hands will cover mouth from the conscious...*"; another participant stated "*...I feel uncomfortable if I cried in front of others so I turn head or use hands to cover my face...*" It seems people are aware of their behaviour and try to do other behaviour to balance the status.

The Effects of Environment

People may incorporate such perceptions in the development of the message when perceiving the environment in a certain way (Knapp and Hall, 2010). The surrounding environment always exerts an influence on nonverbal behaviour.

As one of the participants stated "*...In some serious occasions, I use hand to cover mouth for laughing when I see a funny thing. I know it's impolite...However, in some noise places, I don't think I need to cover mouth for laughing...*" Even we know others very well, we might plan and encode nonverbal behaviours carefully in the serious occasion. One female participant described her opinion "*...For me, it doesn't matter for knowing the person well or not. The most important thing is the occasion...*" In serious occasions, all participants appear to be more concerned about environments

than interpersonal relationships.

The Different Reactions in Gender

Argyle (1990) stated that “men and women behave rather differently in the sphere of bodily communication.” There are many factors such as psychological and innate factors could explain gender differences in NVC. Even in the same situation, men and women might encode different bodily expression to interact with others or environment. In the situation of embarrassment, for example, male participants appear to laugh with others but female participants tend to cover mouth or face with hands.

Creation

Because participants indicated that bodily expression in clips are embarrassment, the goal of creation is creating an avatar’s bodily expression for embarrassment. The drawing software such as CorelDRAW, Adobe Photoshop, and Adobe ImageReady were employed. Two animated images of bodily expression have been created but these two animations were created through two different approaches. One bodily expression was taken directly from movie clips and the other was produced via a scenario-based approach.

Figure 4 Participants demonstrated bodily expression as they explained their observation

Through observing actors’ body movement, all participants could definitely judge actors’ emotions and status. The actor’s body movement was observed in detail, hand and head movement especially. When observing actors’ performance, participants did the same behavior and explained the meaning of bodily expression (Figure 4). All participants indicated that using hands to cover mouth or face when they felt embarrassing in some specific situations. Then, the first avatar’s bodily expression was created: an

avatar covers mouth with hands and turns its head because of belly laugh (Figure 5).

Figure 5 The frame of the first animation

As for the second animation, two Taiwanese males as participants were invited to create a brief scenario. These two participants have work experience so the scenario was created in an office: a bashful male employee is praised for performance achievement in public and he is feeling embarrassed. Several possible bodily expression for this scenario had been discussed and sketched. However, we considered the personality and gender difference as two important factors then removed some concepts. Finally, we decided ‘looking around then scratching head’ as the bodily expression for this scenario (Figure 6).

Figure 6 The frame of the second animation

DISCUSSION

Methods for observing bodily expression

Three possible methods for observing people's bodily expressions have been tested including observations in public places, role-play, and analysing movie clips. Observations in public places might help designers to observe, record and understand bodily expression but this approach appears to be limited.

Role-play was seen as a possible approach because by creating particular scenarios, bodily expression could be observed. However, participants could not present bodily expression well. This method appears to be unproductive in this case although these sources are available.

As for analysing movie clips, professional performances and engaging stories are provided in movies and TV series. The study shows they could offer richer, more useful data for analysing bodily expression. Movies and TV series could be suggested by participants but they do not remember the detail of content. Designers should review these sources and select potential movie clips. Thus, the selections of movie clips still rely on designers' judgements.

Creations

Two animations of an avatar's bodily expression were created via two different methods: movie clips for reference and a scenario-based approach. These two animations were presented to four people separately and feedback was provided in short discussions. Although the two animated images intended to show the status of embarrassment, participants had different opinions about these two animations. Four participants clearly interpreted one animation that presents embarrassment but did not exactly decode the other until the scenario was mentioned.

In the first animation, the avatar covers its mouth with its hands and turns its head. These continuous motions were taken from movie clips and had been interpreted as embarrassment in interviews. Furthermore, movie clips as the reference offered an opportunity to observe the bodily expression in detail.

As for the second animation, an avatar's behaviour is looking around then scratching head. Although this

behaviour was encoded and discussed through a scenario-based approach, this process seems to lack a clear part of reference. According to the reflections above, movie clips could provide more reliable reference for designers and engage participants in creating an avatar's bodily expression.

CONCLUSION

Three possible approaches for observing people's bodily expressions were identified and evaluated in practice: observation in public places, role-play, and analysing movie clips. Observations in public places and role-play appear to be limited and unproductive in this study. Analysing movie clips could be considered as a useful approach to engage people in creating meaningful bodily expression for avatars. This research to date demonstrated two benefits of the use of movie clips: 1. movie clips as artefacts could offer richer, more useful data for analysing bodily expression; 2. movie clips could also provide a more reliable reference for designers and engaging participants in creating an avatar's bodily expression.

Through investigating people's experience and viewpoints on bodily expression with movie clips, the preliminary scheme for understanding in relation to how people decode and interpret bodily expression was concluded as follows: the phenomenon of empathy, the balance of status, the effects of environment, and the different reactions in gender. In the process of decoding-encoding, the ability of empathy for creating an avatar's bodily expression is worth further investigation.

For this research, it took place with a variety of subjects from different cultural backgrounds in the UK and Asia. However, the movie medium and the online gaming medium are both heavily global and participants have many shared ideas evaluated in these environments. Designers who use these methods must be mindful of cultural issues and the particular markets for which they design.

This is the first stage research programme and the

further research will focus on the practical knowledge of transformation of people's bodily expression into an avatar's bodily expression with participants. The outcome will include both evaluated practical methods and a theoretical scheme for understanding the interaction between designers and users.

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